

Thailand as a Viable Regional Education Hub

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to assess Thailand as a viable an education hub in the AEC and Asia Pacific region. Two data primary sets are used in this research. The populations of both surveys are a mix of Thai and non-Thai university students. The instrument used in this research consists of written survey soliciting quantitative, ordinal, and nominal data. The first data set comes from 80 surveys collected from university students in Bangkok to verify the type of education demanded by the market. The preliminary finding of this first data set shows that the market does not have any interests in e-learning platform. The second set of data consists of 98 surveys from the same population taken in subsequent period for further investigation. This experimental design allows the use of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) for potentially new independent variables (IV) not yet treated in the literature. The design also allows Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) for known IVs. An empirical model for Thailand's education hub was derived from this second data set by using the primary data for micro-state and prior years' education market growth of Thailand as macro-state conditions. Education growth rate as part of Thailand's economy was used as a proxy for market trend. Two layers of trend tests were used to verify growth trend in education in Thailand for a period of 10 years. The LaPlace Trend test shows a significant trend at $Z = 33.97$ compared to the theoretical value of 1.65. This finding was confirmed by the MH Trend Test with the result of $\chi_{df,0.95}^2 = 17.47$ compared to the theoretical value of 16.90. This multi-level design is a novel approach in econometric modeling for education market research. The proposed model was tested for reliability and validity by Monte Carlo simulation for which a new iteration method is introduced. The most likelihood estimation (MLE) method was used to validate the model. Significance test was accomplished by Cramer-Rao Lower Bound (CRLB) test, likelihood ration test, Wald statistic and the New Log-Likelihood Estimation (NLLE). This study is a contribution to the field because the proposed model for education hub in Thailand has practical utility.

Key words:

Education hub, Monte Carlo, most likelihood estimation (MLE), new log-likelihood estimation (NLLE)

JEL CODE: C10, C13, C14, C46, E27, G11, G17

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

This is a quantitative research intended to answer the question: “Is Thailand a viable education hub in the ASEAN Economic Community and the global market place?” The objective of this research is to provide a situational analysis for Thailand’s policy goal of becoming an education hub in the ASEAN region. The purpose of this research is two-folds. On the one hand, this paper presents a practical assessment of the viability of Thailand as an education hub in the ASEAN region. On the other, this introduces the use of multiple models in one study; this diversity in methodology is achieved through the use of various types of data obtained from a single instrument. This methodological approach is considered novel for having integrated both discrete and continuous probabilities in one study. The intended contribution of this research is its practical utility for policymakers and stakeholders in education market.

The scope of this research covers both macro- and micro-levels in education market. At the macro-level analysis, 10 years of education growth rate as percentage of the GDP in Thailand is used to verify the education market growth trend. At a micro-level, the research employs psychometric data obtained through survey of Thai and non-Thai students in a private university. Although the concept of education hub is a matter of policy discussion, the use of university student survey helps to assess the market perception of the proposed hub in Thailand. This market perception may render valuable information to policymakers and stakeholders.

This paper is presented in 6 sections. Section 2 reviews the literature on economic hubs and its application in education market. Section 3 describes the data used in the research. Section 4 presents various methodological tools employed in this research. Section 5 presents the findings from and discussion about parametric and non-parametric testing. Section 6 concludes the subject matter with recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Economic hub is defined as the central point around which economic activities revolve (Abeyratne, 2012). The development of education hub resulted from globalization of education. Globalization of education was made possible by information technologies (Knight, 2002). Global education is a bidirectional movement of service providers and consumers. On the one hand, the education service providers move across borders (Knight, 2006). On the other, learners move across border in search for education (Taychaudhuri, 2007). This globalization of education forces tertiary educational institutions to internationalize (Sehoole, 2004). Prior to the year 2000s, the direction of movement of mobile learners had been going from non-OECD to OECD countries (Vebik & Lasanowski, 2007). However, after the mid-2000, there has been a reversal of mobile student flow. Non-OECD countries had fast becoming education destinations for mobile students. This reversal trend was in part due to the internationalization of tertiary education in the non-OECD countries. One element of internationalization is the provision of quality education comparable to standard education in the OECD countries. Not all attempts in internationalization of tertiary education in response to rising demand by mobile students had been successful. India and Nigeria, for instance, responded to the global demand for education service without internationalization and quality control; as the result, India and Nigeria had become known as substandard tertiary education service providers (Obasi, 2007).

Many countries in Southeast Asia announced and implemented the policy of education hub under the banner of internationalization (Dessoff, 2012). These countries include Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, S. Korea and Hong Kong. Their success had been inconsistent. The emergence of education hub is part of the recent development in what has been called “geo-economics” (Khandekar, 2012). The reality of geo-economics has seen the creation of economic hubs in Asia. Asia has become economic hubs in shipping, aviation, energy, commerce and knowledge. Education hub is part of the knowledge arena. Among all contenders in the Asian

education market, only Singapore emerged as a successful player. Thailand enters the fray as a potential candidate of education service provider in Asia’s education hub.

Success in global education market does not depend on price alone. The case of Singapore and Malaysia in the ASEAN market is illustrative of this fact. While the total annual cost in Singapore is \$15,000 and Malaysia costs only \$7,000 yet Singapore ranks at the top of Asia’s education hub. For this reason, price is not used in our modeling. In order to succeed in education hub, the education service provider must maintain a world class status. One writer has put it succinctly that: “An academic culture that is based on meritocratic values, free inquiry, and competition—combined with elements of collaboration and at least some mobility—is central to a world-class university.” (Altbach, 2010, p. 4). For many universities in Asia, these requirements remain a challenge. If Thailand is to succeed as a regional education hub it must become a world class service provider.

Table 1. Market Condition in Global Education Hubs (Figures in US Dollar)

Country Name	Tuition Fee	Living Cost	Total Cost
Australia (public)	\$8,500	\$8,500	\$17,000
Canada (public)	7,000	8,500	15,000
France (public)	Minimal	12,700	12,700
Malaysia (private)	4,000	3,000	7,000
New Zealand (public)	10,000	11,500	21,500
Singapore (private)	6,000	9,000	15,000
UK (public)	13,500	12,500	26,000
US (public)	13,000	12,000	25,000
US (private)	22,000	13,000	35,000

Success in education hub depends on several factors. These factors include (i) awareness by education consumers (learners) that the country is an education hub, (ii) international standing of the country’s education system, and (iii) institutional readiness of the country to accommodate globalization in education. It has been agreed among writers on education hub that only world class universities would succeed (Report on the Development of Education Services in Hong Kong, 2011).

There are four strategic modes in global education that may be adapted for education hub marketing. Mode 1 is characterized by cross-border supplier of education. Mode 2 occurs when learners consume education services abroad. Mode 3 is a model whereby the educational service provider maintains a commercial presence in a foreign market. Lastly, Mode 4 in global education market consists of the presence of natural person of the service provider in the foreign market (OECD-CERI, 2002). Thailand has almost 200 tertiary institutions; a significant number of these institutions could be used to implement education hub policy. Mode 2 may be the most appropriate for Thailand because the promotion of Thailand as an education means that Thailand wants to use the country as service provider in education. Mode 2 targets learners that consume education services abroad. The research question presented by this paper is whether Thailand is a viable education hub? Specifically, we are asking: “Would Thailand succeed in Mode 2 education hub implementation?”

3.0 DATA

The data used in this research comes from three sources. The first set is a secondary data for the growth of education sector as percentage of the GDP. This data is available through the Bank of Thailand’s website. It was used for testing growth trend in the education sector in the past 10 years (2004 – 2014).

The second set of data comes from written questionnaire where 80 surveys were collected. This first set of survey was used to determine whether the market prefer eLearning or conventional classroom learning in Thailand. It was found that eLearning is not a viable platform. Student population still sees conventional classroom learning as necessary learning platform.

The third set of data is comprised of a follow up survey where 98 surveys were collected from a university student population in Bangkok. This second set of 98 samples was bifurcated into two groups according to minimum sample size as required for in-sample testing. The remainder is used for out-of sample testing. Using the *n-Omega* method for non-finite population minimum sample size determination, 35 samples were used for in-sample test. The remaining 43 samples were reserved for out-of-sample testing. The rationale for this sample bifurcation is to ascertain the reproducibility of the empirical findings of the in-sample testing. The sample split used in this research conforms to conventional practice in split sample (Hansen & Timmermann, 2012).

The types of data collected by written survey include quantitative, discrete and nominal data. Quantitative data was affected by continuous scale of (0,1,2,3) where 0 = none, 1 = low, 2 = medium, and 3 = high. The rationale for this type of successive integer scale containing zero is to assure the use of discrete and continuous probability in the data analysis. Instrument calibration was accomplished by the use of per answer choice set reliability equation: $R_q = \sqrt{1 - df(\alpha)}$ where the *df* is the degree of freedom obtained by the number of response choice minus one, and α is the error level, i.e. 5% error level for 95% confidence interval standard. In the present case, the response set has 4 choices; thus: $R_q = \sqrt{1 - 3(0.05)} = \sqrt{0.85}$ or 92.20%, compared to 89.44% under the conventional Likert scale of (1,2,3,4,5).

This study rejects the Likert scale: (1,2,3,4,5) (Likert, 1932; pp. 1-55) as inflexible and inefficient. The Likert scale is inflexible because it does not allow discrete probability analysis due to the absence of zero in the scale. The Likert scale is inefficient because the “lowest” is 1 where as the respondent may want to give “zero” as the lowest and “1” as a low score. This lack of zero and the use of “1” as lowest score create ambiguity. This ambiguity vitiates the accuracy between the score reading and the intent of the respondent (*cf.* Boone & Boone, 2012).

The data in the survey consists of four variables. The *dependent variable* (Y) is defined as institutional readiness for education hub. The factors used to explore institutional readiness include university facilities, teaching staff, and perceived standing of institutional ranking in the regional market. The data type for these three factors is continuous quantitative data. In addition, discrete data in the independent variable composite was also obtained. These discrete data deal with the following questions: (i) could Thailand become an education hub? (ii) could Thailand compete in the education market in the ASEAN region? (iii) does the enrollment of foreign students in Thai universities influences domestic students to study harder, and (iv) the perception of ability of Thai teaching staff in the education global market place. The *independent variables* (Xs) consist of three factors: (i) awareness of Thailand as an education hub, (ii) regional outlook for education, and (iii) instructional materials in Thai university as an indication of international standard. Like the dependent variable, continuous and discrete data were collected. The factors used for dependent variables (DV) and independent variables (IV) in this research are supported by current literature on education hub (Dessoff, 2012). To the extent that the factors in DV and IV are supported by the literature, the proposed model is categorized as Confirmatory Factor Analysis (Yong & Pearson, 2013). The discrete data portions of each variable are considered exploratory to the extent that they are not found in the literature. They are not found in the literature because this research is the first of its kind in Thailand education hub study. If the questions are not supported by the current literature but are relevant to the research issue, they are classified as exploratory and, thus, this portion of the variable constitutes Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) (Hurley, et al., 1997).

This research involves non-finite population. Therefore, random sampling was not possible. A convenience sample method was used. Convenience sampling is defined as non-random and non-

probability sample. A sample is taken from the population without affecting randomization. This purposive sample is some times used when the sample characteristic is not a critical issue in the study, so long as replication may be affected by independent studies, such a sampling method is allowed (Peterson & Merunka, 2014). Convenience sampling is permissible when the sample characteristic is not critical to the research issue (Lucas, 2003) and the sample is not biased (Heckman, 1979). In the present case, college students are used in the sample. The characteristic of the sample is not the overarching issue of the research question. The use of college student as sampling subjects in consumer behavior research had been well documented. It was found that 75% - 86% of consumer research involves college students (Peterson, 2001, and Simonson et al. 2001). So long as the research looks into the psychological process, not the characteristic of the sample, using college student as subjects for the research is permissible (Kardes, 1996).

4.0 METHODOLOGY

In addition to the primary data collected by survey, this research also employed secondary data. The secondary data comes from the Bank of Thailand's macroeconomic indicators for industry contribution to Thailand's GDP. A 10 years data of education sector growth rate was used as a macro-information to test whether there is a growth trend in Thailand's education sector. Trend test was accomplished by the Laplace Trend Test and is verified by the Military Handbook Trend Test (NIST, 2013: §8.2.3.4). The Laplace method is given by:

$$Z_{LTT} = \frac{\sqrt{12r} \sum_{i=1}^r \left(T_i - \frac{T_{end}}{2} \right)}{rT_{end}} \quad (1)$$

The MH method for trend verification is given by:

$$\chi_{2r}^2 = 2 \sum_{i=1}^r \ln \left(\frac{T_{end}}{T_i} \right) \quad (2)$$

The rationale for testing macroeconomic data for trend is to find support for Thailand's education hub policy. If the macroeconomic data does not support a move towards developing education market, the policy of developing Thailand as an education hub would be self-defeating. To that end, proving a growth trend in the education section becomes a necessity.

4.1 Sample Size Calculation

Minimum sample size requirement was met by using the n -Omega method (Louangrath, 2014). Under the n_{Ω} method, minimum sample size is determined by:

$$n_{\Omega} = \sqrt{\frac{\left[\left(\frac{Z^2 \sigma^2}{E^2} \right) / 0.01 \right] - \left[\left(\frac{Z \sigma}{E} \right) / 0.99 \right]}{2}} \quad (3)$$

According to n_{Ω} method, the minimum sample size is 33.72 for 95% confidence interval. In this research a total of 98 samples were collected. From this number 35 samples were used for in-sample testing and the remaining 43 were used for out-of-sample testing. The sample sizes for in-

sample and out-of-sample tests meet the minimum sample size requirement. For minimum sample size table with confidence interval under the n_{Ω} method.

4.2 Data Distribution Verification

Data distribution verification was tested in two stages. In the first stage, the data were checked for significant outliers under extreme value theory using the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) approach according to the Fisher-Tippett-Gnedenko method. In the second stage, distribution test was accomplished under Anderson-Darling test.

The Fisher-Tippett-Gnedenko GEV is given by:

$$H(x; \mu, \sigma, \xi) = \exp \left\{ - \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \right) \right]^{-1/\xi} \right\} \quad (4)$$

where μ = location; σ = scale; and ξ = shape. If $\xi > 0$, H becomes a cumulative distribution function (CDF); if $\xi < 0$, it is valid for $x < \mu + \sigma / (-\xi)$; and if $\xi = 0$, H is undefined. (Bensalah, 2000). However, if $\xi \rightarrow 0$, then (4) is reduced to:

$$H(x; \mu, \sigma, 0) = \exp \left\{ - \left(\frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \right) \right\} \quad (5)$$

The parameter ξ is the tail index of the distribution. This index may be used to classify the type of extreme value distribution. If $\xi = 0$, the H distribution is Gumbel distribution, also known as Type I where $x \in \mathfrak{R}$ and $\xi = 0$. The Gumbel distribution is given by:

$$H(x; \mu, \sigma, 0) = \exp \left\{ - \exp \left(\frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \right) \right\} \quad (6)$$

If $\xi > 0$, the H distribution is a Fréchet distribution or Type II. The Fréchet distribution is given by:

$$H(x; \mu, \sigma, \xi) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } x < \mu \\ \exp \left\{ \left(\frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^{-\alpha} \right\} & \text{for } x > \mu \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

If $\xi < 0$, the H distribution is Weibull distribution or Type III. The Weibull distribution is given by:

$$H(x; \mu, \sigma, \xi) = \begin{cases} \exp \left\{ - \left(- \left(\frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \right) \right) \right\}^{-\alpha} & \text{for } x < \mu \\ 1 & \text{for } x \geq \mu \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Extreme value distribution is classified by the tail index. There are two methods for the tail index estimation: the Pickands method (Pickands, 1975), and the Hill method. (Wagner and Marsh, 2000). Firstly, the Pickands method is given by:

$$\hat{\xi}_{k,m} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^k (\ln X_{n-i+1} - \ln X_{n-m}) \quad (9)$$

where m = number of observations whose tail is to be observed and k = sample size. Secondly, the Hill method is given by:

$$\hat{\xi}_{k,T} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k (\ln R_{i,T} - \ln R_{k,T}) \quad (10)$$

where $R = \sigma Z$; σ is the estimated population standard deviation and Z is the standard score of the series: $Z = (x_i - \bar{x})/S$. Both methods follows the same conditions in providing the decision rule for classifying the type of extreme value distribution: *Frechet* = $\xi > 0$, *Weibull* = $\xi < 0$ and *Gumbel* = $\xi = 0$.

If the data does not contain extreme values, the second stage of the distribution verification is to ascertain whether the data is normally distributed. This second distribution test is accomplished by the Anderson-Darling test which is given by:

$$AD = -n - S^* \quad (11)$$

$$S^* = \sum \left(\frac{2i-1}{n} \right) \ln F(Z) + \ln(1 - F(Z)) \quad (12)$$

The result in (12) is compared with the theoretical value given by AD^* where:

$$AD^* = AD \left(1 + \frac{0.75}{n} + \frac{2.25}{n^2} \right) \quad (13)$$

The data is normally distributed if $AD \leq AD^*$, otherwise it is not normally distributed if $AD > AD^*$.

4.3 Randomness Verification

There are two types of data probabilities used in this research, namely continuous and discrete probabilities. It is necessary to verify that the data set is comprised of random values. Most statistically tests require that the data be random (Rukhin et al, 2001). In this research, randomness test for continuous data was accomplished by the adjacent test (Basein, 1996; Doob, 1953; Lawler, 1995; Parzen, 1962; Ito, 1987A; and Ito, 1987B). The adjacent test is given by:

$$L_{<25} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (X_{i+1} - X_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2} \quad (14)$$

The decision rule is governed by the assumption that the data set is random if the test statistic falls within the range of $a < L < b$. The value of this range is given in the L Table provided

by Hart (1942), *see* Appendix 1. In the present case, the first 25 items of quantitative data are used for testing.

Data that are treated under discrete probability may be tested for randomness under the NIST's monobit method:

$$S_{obs} = \frac{|S_n|}{\sqrt{n}} \quad \text{where } S_n = \sum (+,-)_i \quad (15)$$

The observed value S_{obs} is compared to the theoretical value:

$$Z_{mono} = \frac{S_{obs}}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (16)$$

The decision rule is governed by: $H_0: Z \leq 1.65$ which means that the number set is random otherwise $H_A: Z > 1.65$ which means that the data set is not random.

4.4 Linear regression Modeling

4.4.1 Simple Linear Regression

Linear regression is based on ordinary least squares (OLS) method to predict linear relationship between dependent variable (DV = Y) and independent variable (IV = X) using mean difference as the building block (Faraway, 2002). Although linear regression is a common tool for relationship modeling, its application is limited to the linearity among quantitative data. For non-quantitative data, other types of methodological tools are required.

Where the independent variable (X) is quantitative and the dependent variable (Y) is also quantitative, a common predictive function is linear regression. For single explanatory (X), a simple linear regression is used. For two or more explanatory variables (Xs) explaining Y, a multiple linear regression is used. The simple regression is given by:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \varepsilon \quad (17)$$

where Y = what needs to be explained or the event or institutional readiness for education hub; β_0 = intercept of Y or the value of Y without the explanatory variable X , i.e. a point on the Y -axis where X is zero; β_1 = the parameter to be estimate or the coefficient (multiplier) of X ; this value is unknown and could be estimated with empirical data; X = explanatory factor or the variable that explains the occurrence on Y . The term ε is the forecast error. The objective of the alternative hypothesis is to prove that $\beta_0 \neq 0$.

The test statistic for the simple linear regression is given by a T-test for the Pearson correlation coefficient:

$$T_r = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}} \quad (18)$$

where the correlation coefficient r is given by $r = b(S_x/S_y)$ within the range of $-1 < r < 1$. Other types of correlation coefficients are used depending on the type of data combination between DV and IV.

Table 2. Correlation Coefficient according to Data Type Combination

Variable	Quantitative	Ordinal	Nominal
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(X,Y)	X	X	X
Quantitative Y	Pearson r	Biserial r_b	Point Biserial r_{pb}
Ordinal Y	Biserial r_b	Spearman $rho \rho$ Tetrachoric & Polychoric	Rank biserial c
Nominal Y	Point Biserial r_{pb}	Rank biserial r_{rb}	ϕ , L, C and λ

In this paper, the simple regression models for Thailand’s education hub study are given by:

$$Y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + e_1 \quad \text{where } X_1 = \text{aware of Thailand as an education hub};$$

$$Y_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_2 X_2 + e_2 \quad \text{where } X_2 = \text{regional outlook of Thailand’s standing}; \text{ and}$$

$$Y_3 = \beta_0 + \beta_3 X_3 + e_3 \quad \text{where } X_3 = \text{perceived standard of education delivery}.$$

4.4.2 Multiple Linear Regression

In a case where there are two or more explanatory variables (Xs), the multiple regression model is used. Multiple regression model is given by:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_p X_p + \varepsilon \tag{19}$$

The objective is to prove that all $\beta_{i>0}$ coefficients are non-zero. Significance test in the multiple regression model is the test for the variance vector of Y. If the proposed model is a good predictor, the difference between $Y_i - \hat{Y}_i$ should be within an acceptable error level. For 95% confidence interval, the permissible error level should not exceed 5%.

The test statistic for the multiple regression is the F-test for variance analysis, i.e. ANOVA (analysis of variance) which is given by:

$$F = \frac{MSR}{MSE} \tag{20}$$

$$MSR = \frac{SSR}{p} \tag{20.1}$$

$$SSR = \sum (\hat{Y}_i - \bar{Y})^2 \tag{20.2}$$

$$MSE = \frac{SSE}{n - p - 1} \tag{20.3}$$

$$SSE = \sum (Y_i - \hat{Y})^2 \tag{20.4}$$

The F-test for the multiple regression is a tool to assess the adequacy of the model. It answers the question of: “how well can the model explain the data?” The result of the multiple regression may be summarized in ANOVA table as shown in Table 2.

Table 3. ANOVA Table for Multiple Linear Regression Model

Source of Error	SS Sum Squares	Degree of Freedom	MS Mean Squares	F Statistic
Model / Group	SSR	$n - 1$	$MSR = \frac{SSR}{p}$	$F = \frac{MSR}{MSE}$
Residual / Error	SSE	$n - p - 1$	$MSE = \frac{SSE}{n - p - 1}$	
Total	$SST = SSR + SSE$	$n - 1$		

Multiple regression was used in this research by defining Y as the institutional readiness for education hub. The independent variables were X1 = awareness of Thailand as a hub; X2 = regional outlook among learners of the education market in the ASEAN; and X3 = operational readiness for education hub, such as teaching materials and university facilities. The proposed multiple regression models are:

$$Y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e_1; \quad (A)$$

$$Y_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e_2; \quad (B)$$

$$Y_3 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_3 X_3 + e_3; \text{ and} \quad (C)$$

$$Y_4 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e_4 \quad (D)$$

The general matrix form of the proposed models may be represented in a conventional form, thus:

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & x_{11} & x_{12} & x_{13} \\ 1 & x_{21} & x_{22} & x_{23} \\ \dots & & \dots & \\ 1 & x_{n1} & x_{n2} & x_{n3} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ \dots \\ y_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \dots \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \mu + \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \dots \\ \varepsilon_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (E)$$

4.4.3 Coefficient of Determination R^2

The power of the model to explain the data is called the coefficient of determination or R^2 . The R^2 measure tells us the percentage that the proposed model could explain the data. For instance, if $R^2 = 0.80$, it means that the proposed model could explain 85% of the data and the remaining 20% could not be explained.¹ This is also an indication that the proposed model contains incomplete variables. The R^2 for simple linear regression is given by:

$$R^2 = \left[b \left(\frac{S_x}{S_y} \right) \right]^2 \quad (21)$$

¹ The general interpretation of R-squared is the ability of the model to explain the data. However, in a case where the variables are supported by the literature but the result shows that R-square is low, this may be evidence of disinformation between policy and the public. For instance, in this research, the issue of education hub is a macro-policy; the survey of college students' perception (consumer of education service) is a micro-behavior. A low R-square does not mean that the model is invalid, but in fact, it shows that there is still a dissonance between policy and practice, i.e. the education market is not yet fully informed about the education policy. The low R-square value in this case serves as a feedback mechanism for policymaker.

where b = slope of the regression line; S_x = standard deviation of the array X; and S_y = standard deviation of the array Y. The limit of R^2 is 1 since the range of correlation coefficient r is $-1 < r < 1$.

The coefficient of determination for the multiple regression is given by the sum of the product of β_i multiplied by x_{1y} :

$$R^2 = \sum \beta_i r_{x1y} \quad (22)$$

where the β_i term is the coefficient of each explanatory variable (IV). If the multiple regression model has two explanatory variables X1 and X2, then the coefficient β_i are respectively:

$$\beta_1 = \frac{r_{x1y} - r_{x1x2}r_{x2y}}{1 - r_{x1x2}^2} \quad (23)$$

$$\beta_2 = \frac{r_{x2y} - r_{x1x2}r_{x1y}}{1 - r_{x1x2}^2} \quad (24)$$

The value of R^2 in (21) not adjusted for its degrees of freedom and the number of parameters used. The adjusted R^2 is given by:

$$\tilde{R}^2 = 1 - (1 - R^2) \left[\frac{n-1}{n-p-1} \right] \quad (25)$$

4.4.4 Interaction Effect in Multiple Regression

This paper measures the interaction effect among IV. Even if under multiple regression shows that the model is vitiated as the result of low R-square value, the model is still worth pursuing if there is significant interaction effect among IV to produce Y. In this research, there are three independent variables explaining the outcome of Y such that: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon$, there should be a further investigation whether there is an interaction between X_1 , X_2 and X_3 . The interaction effect model is given by:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_3 X_1 X_2 + \beta_4 X_2 X_3 + \beta_3 X_1 X_3 + \varepsilon \quad (26)$$

The interaction term is given by $\beta_3 X_1 X_2$. The coefficient for the interaction β_3 is obtained through:

$$\beta_3 = \hat{\beta} - \beta_1 - \beta_2 - \beta_0 \quad (26.1)$$

$$\hat{\beta} = \bar{Y} - (\beta_2 + \beta_0) - \beta_1 \quad (26.2)$$

The test statistic to verify whether the interaction effect $\beta_3 X_1 X_2$ is statistically significant is given by:

$$T_{x_1 x_2} = \frac{\beta_1 - \beta_2}{\sqrt{\frac{n_1 SE_1^2 + n_2 SE_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}}} \quad (27)$$

In this research, we want to measure the interaction effect between X1 (awareness of Thailand as an education hub, X2 (regional outlook of Thailand's education in ASEAN), and X3 (perceived standard of Thailand's education in the global market place). Significant interaction effect tells us that IVs are not fully independent; individual IV interacts to produce the value of Y. this measurement is an important issue to study because interaction effect measurement allows us to see the latent values that are not readily observable.

4.5 Non-Linear Modeling

4.5.1 Logit Model for Discrete Data

The survey used in this research also collects discrete data. Discrete data is also called categorical data. Categorical data is the type of data that is scored (1, 0). The 1 and 0 comes from the construction of data categories where 1 denotes the type of response that the researcher is seeking, i.e. sex, age group, education level, income level, etc. Whenever this “category of interest” is found, it is given a score of 1. In this research, all variables (Y & X) contains discrete data. The probability of success is given by the Laplace Rule of Succession:²

$$p = \frac{s+1}{n+2} \quad (28)$$

where s = number of success counts, and n = sample size. The probability of failure is simply:

$$q = 1 - p \quad (29)$$

These two probabilities p and q provides the basis for logit model and all discrete probability analysis. The descriptive statistics of the discrete or binomial distribution data are: (i) mean: $\bar{X} = np$ and (ii) variance: $\text{var}(y_i) = npq$.

The standard logit model is given by:

² Laplace, Pierre-Simon (1814). *Essai philosophique sur les probabilités*. Paris: Courcier. The La Place Rule of Succession: $p = (s+1)/(n+2)$ comes from the following text: “Thus we find that an event having occurred successively any number of times, the probability that it will happen again the next time is equal to this number increased by unity divided by the same number, increased by two units.” (English translation, p. 19. Trans. from the 6th French edition by F.W. Truscott & F.I. Emory (1902)). The original text of the first edition reads: “On trouve ainsi qu'un événement étant arrivé de suite un nombre quelconque de fois, la probabilité qu'il arrivera encore la fois suivante est égale à ce nombre augmenté de l'unité, divisé par le même nombre augmenté de deux unités.” Piere Simon La Place (1840). *Essai Philosophique sur les Probabilités*; ed. 1st, p. 23.

$$\log\left(\frac{p_{ij}}{1-p_{ij}}\right) = X'_{ij}\beta + \underline{\delta}_j \quad (30)$$

This is the same as saying:

$Y_{\log} = \log\left(\frac{p_{ij}}{1-p_{ij}}\right)$ and $Y_{\log} = X'_{ij}\beta + \underline{\delta}_j$ where Y is what needs to be explained. The terms of equation (30) are defined as: $j =$ level of units or cluster where $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$; $I =$ level-1 units or nested observations where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$; and $n = \sum_{j=1}^N n_j$ is the total number of level-1 observations across level-2. Note that the logit model is actually the ratio between p and q :

$$\log\left(\frac{p_{ij}}{1-p_{ij}}\right) = \log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \log\left(\frac{p}{q}\right) \quad (31)$$

This intuitive appeal does not require proof since it is a straight forward algebraic substitution of terms.³ The model described in (30) is used in dichotomous data (1,0) for level-1 nested in level-2 $_j$. The logit model is written in terms of log odds. The model is stated as

$X'_{ij}\beta + \underline{\delta}_j$ where the terms of the model are defined as:

X_{ij} = SX1 covariate vector include 1 for the intercept;

β = SX1 vector of unknown regression parameter; and

$\underline{\delta}_j$ = random cluster effect (one for each level-2 cluster) which is distributed $N(0,1)$ for

$\underline{\delta}_j = \sigma_{\delta}\theta_j$; thus, the model in (30) becomes:

$$\log\left(\frac{p_{ij}}{1-p_{ij}}\right) = X'_{ij}\beta + \underline{\delta}_{\delta}\theta_j \quad (32)$$

³ Under the DeMoivre-Laplace Theorem (DLT), as $n \rightarrow \infty$, the discrete distribution of the dichotomous data (discrete data) will approximate a normal distribution as expressed by the Gaussian function $g(x)$:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Pr\left[\frac{x-np}{\sqrt{npq}}\right] \leq \Phi(z) \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad g(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2\right]$$

Therefore, it is possible that DLT may be used as the basis of statistical significance test in logit modeling. This potential is explored in the later section of this writing. See Balazs, M. & Toth, B. (2014). "Stirling's Formula and De Moivre-Laplace Central Limit Theorem." Online access: http://www.maths.bris.ac.uk/~mb13434/Stirling_DeMoivre_Laplace.pdf

This is called the *random effect model*. It is used for ordinal data. The coefficient $\underline{\delta}_\delta$ and $\underline{\theta}_j$ are the variances of the random effects. The term $\underline{\delta}_\delta$ is called the random effects variance.

One purpose of the logit model is to serve as a tool to measure latent variable. Latent variable is defined as “observable” variable that affects the response variable (Ping, 1996; and Steinmetz et al, 2011) Under this conceptual framework, there are two variates that are responsible for the occurrence of the dependent variable, namely response variable \underline{Y} and its corresponding latent variable \underline{y} . Now define the following terms as:

\underline{y} = a latent continuous variable.⁴ It is called “latent” because ordinal data measures something that is not generally observable, i.e. 1st, 2nd, ... choice of preference, etc.;

\underline{Y} = observed dichotomous response, i.e. 1st, 2nd, ...;

γ = *gamma* threshold determine if the dichotomous response is equal to 0 ($\underline{y}_{ij} \leq \gamma$) or 1 ($\underline{y}_{ij} > \gamma$). If the threshold gamma is set to zero ($\gamma = 0$) then \underline{y} follows either normal or logistic probability density function (PDF) as shown in the figure below.

We can now write the predictive function in terms of the latent variable \underline{y} as:

$$\underline{y}_{ij} = X'_{ij}\beta + Z'_{ij}T\underline{\theta}_j + \underline{\varepsilon}_{ij} \tag{34}$$

where $\underline{\varepsilon}_{ij}$ = the error in logistic model. This error is assumed to follow logistic distribution with mean 0 and variance $\pi^2/3$ or $\log(0, \pi^2/3)$. The shape of the logit model is an S-shape. The S-shape is commonly used to model the growth function:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 - e^{-z_i}} \tag{35}$$

where $z_i = \beta_0 + \beta'X$ which is the logit function described in (30) and its extensions through (35). The log-likelihood used for estimating the logit is given by:

$$\ln L(\beta_0, \beta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[Y_i \ln \left(\frac{e^{z_i}}{1 + e^{z_i}} \right) + (1 - Y_i) \ln \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{z_i}} \right) \right] \tag{36}$$

where the parent function for the log-likelihood function is given by:

$$\ln L(Y) = \sum Y_i \ln F(Z) + (1 - Y_i) \ln(1 - F(Z)) \tag{36.1}$$

⁴ Note that *dichotomous data* are discrete: (1, 0). Variable \underline{y} presented here is the measure of “latent continuous variable”. There should not be any confusion for the use of terms: “discrete” and “continuous” in the same context. The latent response is obtained via discrete data classification, i.e. (yes | no); this scoring is the discrete in that it scores the response to individual question asked by the researcher. The question attempts to measure a “latent variable”, i.e. not observable but possibly continuous; thus the variable \underline{y} is called continuous latent variable.

With correction:

$$\ln L(Y) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum Y_i \ln F(Z) + (1-Y_i) \ln(1-F(Z)) \quad (36.2)$$

Equation (36) is obtained by substituting equation (35) into the term $F(Z)$ or the percentage probability in equation (36.1). The log-likelihood will produce the expected value for the proposed logit model. This expected value is compared with the observed logit value. Thus, the query of whether the proposed model fulfilled the requirement of best fit under goodness-of-fit (GOF) protocol; GOF could be used for hypothesis testing. This conventional likelihood function is modified and improved in (37) – (39) below.

4.6 Repeated Measurement and Simulation for Out-of-Sample Testing

This paper proposes to use the modified log likelihood function in order to reduce the bias or inaccuracy between the arithmetic mean and the expected value. The proposed function consists of two steps: (i) determine the log likelihood of $(X_i : x_1, \dots, x_n)$ under the new LLE, and (ii) adjust the estimate the LLE in (i) by subtracting $(\ln L(X))^{-n-1}$. The proposed log-likelihood in step 1 is given by:

$$\ln L(X) = \sum \left(\frac{X_i \ln F(Z)}{n-1} \right) + \left(\frac{(1-X_i)(1-F(Z))}{n^2 = n-1} \right) \quad (37)$$

With the estimate obtained in (37), the expected value for $(X_i : x_1, \dots, x_n)$ is obtained through:

$$E[X] = \frac{1}{n} \sum (X_i - \ln(X_i)) - \left| \frac{\sum \ln L(X)}{n-1} \right| \quad (38)$$

The result of (38) is always almost equal to $\bar{X} \cong E[X]$ and, thus, the bias for the estimator is minimized. Under this proposed log-likelihood estimator function, the arithmetic mean is equal to the expected value. The modification does not affect the value of the Fisher information for purposes of asymptotic normality analysis. Note that if the denominator of the correcting factor is n such that:

$$E[X] = \frac{1}{n} \sum (X_i - \ln(X_i)) - \left| \frac{\sum \ln L(X)}{n} \right| \quad (39)$$

The expected value is observationally equivalent to the arithmetic mean of the series $(X_i : x_1, \dots, x_n)$, this violates the property of *identity* of likelihood function where the condition $\hat{\theta} \rightarrow \theta$, but $\hat{\theta} \neq \theta$ must be maintained. Therefore, in (38) following the Bessel correction approach, the degree of freedom is used (Cho & Cho, 2008).

Under the new LLE method, the Fisher information $(I(\theta_0))$ is calculated by $I(\theta_0) = 1/\text{var}[X_i - \ln L(X_i) - |\ln L(X_i)/n-1|]$. The likelihood function is used to test the reproducibility and consistency of result from the proposed model. In this research, it was found that the multiple regression failed for autocorrelation among IVs, but shows significant interactions.

Likewise, all simple regression pairs between DV and IV shows statistical significance. These functional simple regressions models had been put through Monte Carlo simulation in order to test for reproducibility in out-of-sample testing.

4.6.1 A Proposed Test for New LLE under Chi Square

The proposed test statistic for the new LLE method follows chi square test statistic in form:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{(n-1)S_{\ln L(X)}^2}{\sigma_{E[X]}^2} \Bigg|_{df=n-1} \tag{40}$$

where n is the sample size; $S_{\ln L(X)}^2$ is the variance of the new $\ln L(X)$ under equation (37), and $\sigma_{E[X]}^2$ is the estimated variance of the $E[X]$. The critical value for the null hypothesis is read from the chi square table at degree of freedom $n-1$. Table 5 answer the query where the data is quantitative and continuous; if the data set is discrete, then we need a different approach under chi square test. Recall that the chi square test for discrete case is generally given by:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{(n-1)(ad - bc)^2}{(a+b)(a+c)(b+d)(c+d)} \tag{41}$$

where the terms a , b , c , and d are the frequency counts from the 2×2 contingency table. To apply (41) to the new log-likelihood case, it is necessary to first construct a 2×2 table where the observed frequency may be recorded as shown below.

Table 4. Using 2×2 as the Basis for Chi Square Testing for Discrete Data

	Class 1	Class 2	Total
Sample 1	a	b	$a + b$
Sample 2	c	d	$c + b$
Total	$a + c$	$b + d$	$N = a + b + c + d$

The “class” term may be defined as $\ln L(X) = \text{Class1}$ and $E[X] = \text{Class2}$ under the new log-likelihood method. “Sample1” and “sample 2” may represent two independent samples taken for the same study or split-samples from one original sample, *see* Timmermann (2012).

5.0 FINDINGS

There are two parts to the presentation of the findings: (i) preliminary testing of the data, and (ii) hypothesis testing for the proposed model. The preliminary tests include (a) trend test for the growth in education sector, (b) data distribution test, and (c) randomness testing. Findings for hypothesis tests are presented in 5 sections. Section 1 of the finding explores consumer awareness of Thailand as an education hub. The level of awareness indicates the level of effectiveness of policymakers conveying its policy to the market. Section 2 provides information about the consumer’s outlook on Thailand’s education in the global market. Section 3 provides perception measurement of non-Thai students in Thai university on the issue of whether the delivery pf education and teaching meets international standard. Section 4 assesses Thailand’s institutional readiness as a key indicator for succeeding in regional education hub. Lastly, section 5 provides the simulation test of the proposed model under Monte Carlo simulation method.

The test for growth trend in education sector in Thailand was accomplished by the Laplace Trend Test:

$$Z_{LTT} = \frac{\sqrt{12r} \sum_{i=1}^r \left(T_i - \frac{T_{end}}{2} \right)}{rT_{end}}$$

Table 5. Laplace Trend Test of Education Sector as Percentage of GDP (Thailand)

Year	Education %	$T - \left(\frac{T_{end}}{2} \right)$	rT_{end}	$\sqrt{12r} \sum_{i=1}^r \left(T_i - \frac{T_{end}}{2} \right)$
2005	5.30	4.25	21.00	= 259.18 $rT_{end} = 21$ $Z_{LTT} = \frac{259.18}{21} = 12.34$ $H_0 : Z \leq 1.65$ $H_A : Z > 1.65$
2006	2.00	0.95	21.00	
2007	3.30	2.25	21.00	
2008	4.40	3.35	21.00	
2009	0.06	- 0.99	21.00	
2010	4.10	3.05	21.00	
2011	5.20	4.15	21.00	
2012	2.80	1.75	21.00	
2013	4.90	3.85	21.00	
2014	2.10	1.05	21.00	

The result of the Laplace trend test shows that the education sector as a percentage of Thailand’s annual GDP is a significant growing trend.

The second preliminary data test is the distribution test. The first step in data distribution test is to verify if there are significant outliers that would lead to the presence of extreme values. The standard score equation is used to find extreme values: $Z = (x_i - \bar{x}) / S$. From the annual education growth rate for 10 years from 2005 to 2014, the maximum and minimum points are used to determine whether there are extreme values in the set. The maximum value is 5.30 and minimum value is 0.06. The upper bound is $Z_U = 1.38$; thus, there is no extreme value in the higher end of the growth. The lower bound is $Z_L = -2.87$; since this value is smaller than -1.65, the lower bound of the set contains extreme value. The result of the test appears to be inconclusive. However, since the trend test shows that there is a growing trend, we may disregard the lower bound extremity and focus on the upper bound.

The third preliminary data test is the test for normality under the Anderson-Darling test. The observed value is 8.24. This value is compared with the theoretical value of:

$$AD^* = AD \left(1 + \frac{0.75}{n} + \frac{2.25}{n^2} \right) = 8.24 \left(1 + \frac{0.75}{10} + \frac{2.25}{10^2} \right) = 8.24(1.0975) = 9.04$$

The education sector’s growth over the past 10 years is normally distributed and shows a positive trend. Thailand’s attempt to pursue education hub policy may be in the right direction.

5.1 In-Sample non-Parametric Testing

The in-sample testing uses 40 counts of the survey collected from the field. The non-parametric testing for in-sample consists of the test for data distribution and randomness. Distribution test was accomplished by the Anderson-Darling test to verify whether the data is normally distributed. The decision rule for the AD test is $H_0 : AD \leq AD^* \Rightarrow$ Normally distributed and $H_0 : AD > AD^* \Rightarrow$ Not normally distributed. Secondly, the test for randomness was accomplished by the adjacent Test. The decision rule for the adjacent test is $H_0 : 1.37 < L < 2.63 \Rightarrow$ Random, and

H_A : Not in the range $1.37 < L < 2.63 \Rightarrow$ Not random . The findings of these non-parametric in-sample tests are summarized in Table 7.

Table 6. In-Sample Non-Parametric Testing of Independent Variables

Type of Tests Non-Parametric $n = 40$	X1 <i>Awareness of Thailand as Education Hub</i>	X2 <i>Regional outlook Of Thailand's Education</i>	X3 <i>Perceived Instructional Delivery</i>
Anderson-Darling Test for Normality $AD < AD^*$	AD = 29.12 AD* = 39.91 Normally distributed	AD = 26.81 AD* = 27.35 Normally distributed	AD = 26.86 AD* = 27.40 Normally Distributed
Adjacent Test for Randomness $1.37 < L < 2.63$	L(obs) = 1.83 $1.37 < L < 2.63$ Random	L(obs) = 1.87 $1.37 < L < 2.63$ Random	L(obs) = 2.30 $1.37 < L < 2.63$ Random

5.2 Out-of-Sample non-Parametric Testing

From 98 samples collected, 40 samples were used for in-sample testing. The remaining 58 samples were used for out-of-sample testing. Out-of-sample test is conducted for purposes of verifying the reproducibility of the model and to see the consistency of the data. The non-parametric out-of-sample data testing results are summarized in Table 9.

Table 8. Out-of-Sample Non-Parametric Testing for Independent Variables

Type of Tests Non-Parametric $n = 58$	X1 <i>Awareness of Thailand as Education Hub</i>	X2 <i>Regional outlook Of Thailand's Education</i>	X3 <i>Perceived Instructional Delivery</i>
Anderson-Darling Test for Normality $AD < AD^*$	AD = 349.62 AD* = 354.37 Normally distributed	AD = 28.70 AD* = 29.09 Normally distributed	AD = 89.64 AD* = 90.88 Normally distributed
Adjacent Test for Randomness $1.37 < L < 2.63$	L(obs) = 2.41 $1.37 < L < 2.63$ Random	L(obs) = 2.06 $1.37 < L < 2.63$ Random	L(obs) = 2.42 $1.37 < L < 2.63$ Random

5.3 In-Sample Parametric Testing

There are two sets of parametric testing: simple regression, and multiple regression. For simple regression modeling, the following results were obtained:

$$Y = 1.37 + 0.33X_{aware} \text{ with } T = 2.91 \text{ \& } R^2 = 0.18$$

$$Y = 1.37 + 0.33X_{outlook} \text{ with } T = 2.91 \text{ \& } R^2 = 0.18$$

$$Y = 1.37 + 0.33X_{teaching} \text{ with } T = 2.14 \text{ \& } R^2 = 0.11$$

It is not common to find this uniformity of the parameter in three different models. Since each IV asks questions concerning different issues, it is expected that the parameter for each

variable would be different. However, in this case, both the intercept and the estimated parameter for X1 (awareness of Thailand as an education hub, X2 (regional outlook on Thailand's educational ranking), and X3 (teaching delivery by Thai instructors) are identify for three explanatory factors. Although all the variables in simple regression modeling shows statistically significant relationship between IV and DV, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is low indicating that the simple regression may not be adequate to explain the data, i.e. multiple regression must be explored.

When the IVs are put into multiple regression modeling, it was found that X1 and X2 had perfect autocorrelation and thus vitiated multiple regression for the combination of X1 and X2. Thus, the only remaining variable combinations are (X1,X3) and (X2,X3). The result of these remaining variable combination for multiple regression are given by:

$$Y = 1.15 + 0.29X_{outlook} + 0.17X_{teaching}$$

$$Y = 1.15 + 0.29X_{aware} + 0.17X_{teaching}$$

The same values for the intercept and parameter for IVs are also observed in multiple regression models. The ANOVA analyses for the two models are given as: $F(39,39) = 1.69$ for the expected value and the empirical value is $F = 0.18$ for $Y = 1.15 + 0.29X_{outlook} + 0.17X_{teaching}$. An identical F value is found for $Y = 1.15 + 0.29X_{aware} + 0.17X_{teaching}$. These two readings of the F test tell us that multiple linear regression is not an appropriate model. Further tests need to be conducted to explore whether a polynomial model is appropriate or non-linear models, such as probit and logit may be used.

Interaction effect measurements for the two variable pairs: X2X3 and X1X3 were made:

$$T_{x2x3} = \frac{\beta_1 - \beta_2}{\sqrt{\frac{n_1 SE_1^2 + n_2 SE_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}}} = \frac{0.29 - 0.17}{\sqrt{\frac{40(0.24) + 40(0.28)}{40 + 40 - 2}}} = \frac{0.12}{\sqrt{\frac{9.6 + 11.2}{78}}} = \frac{0.12}{\sqrt{\frac{20.80}{78}}} = \frac{0.12}{\sqrt{0.27}} \quad \text{The same}$$

$$T_{x1x2} = \frac{0.12}{0.52} = 0.23$$

calculation made for the interaction between X1 and X3 obtaining $T_{x1x3} = 0.23$ which is not statistically significant.

The unexpected outcome of this research is explained by the fact that "education hub" is a national issue. This issue is generally discussed by policymakers at the national level. The survey in this research comes from psychometric measurement of college students, i.e. student perception of institutional readiness for education hub. This type of survey requires that the subject of the study possess an appreciable degree of knowledge about education hub policy. The result here shows that there is a dissonance between policy level and the market, i.e. college students, about Thailand's education hub. The public or the market is not fully informed about the policy. The practical value of this research is its feedback effect for policymakers that the public or education consumers may not be fully informed about education hub in Thailand. This assertion is validated by the mean score of X1 = 2.02, X2 = 2.02 and X3 = 1.90.

5.4 Out-of-Sample Parametric Testing

The out-of-sample test was obtained through a re-run of the remaining 58 sample counts. The same results were obtained.

6.0 CONCLUSION

Thailand has a good potential of becoming an education hub in the ASEAN region. With almost 200 tertiary institutions, the country possesses the physical infrastructure that could rival its ASEAN partners and other non-ASEAN player in the region. The recent growth trend in the

education sector as percentage of the country GDP points in a positive direction. However, the concept of education hub remains a policy discussion. In order to put it into practice, the public, especially education service consumers must be more informed about the country's hub objective. This paper discussed various hub modes pursue elsewhere; an appropriate education hub model that is more appropriate for Thailand is known as Mode 2 (consuming education abroad), i.e. Thailand would be a service providers and service consumers are foreign students. This mode 2 approach would turn Thailand into a global education market place. As such the country must become a "world class" education service provider. Universities in Thailand participating in implementing this policy of education hub must strive to become "world class universities."

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APPENDIX 1

L Table for Adjacent Test of Randomness

Two-sided One-sided	Significance Level: α			
	0.10		0.02	
	0.05		0.01	
<i>n</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>
4	0.78	3.22	0.63	3.37
5	0.82	3.18	0.54	3.46
6	0.89	3.11	0.56	3.44
7	0.94	3.06	0.61	3.39
8	0.98	3.02	0.66	3.34
9	1.02	2.98	0.71	3.29
10	1.06	2.94	0.75	3.25
11	1.10	2.90	0.79	3.21
12	1.13	2.87	0.83	3.17
15	1.21	2.79	0.92	3.08
20	1.30	2.70	1.04	2.98
25	1.37	2.63	1.13	2.87

The critical value of L at various significance levels. Lower bound = *a* and upper bound = *b*. Source: Hart, B.I. (1942). "Significance Level for the Mean Square Successive Difference to the Variance." *Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, **13**: 445-7.